

The Impact of Vaccination Campaigns on Measles Incidence and Mortality: A Comparative Historical Analysis

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of vaccination campaigns on measles incidence and mortality in three countries with robust historical data: the United Kingdom (UK), the United States (US), and the Soviet Union (USSR). By analyzing detailed statistics from 1940 to 1990, we demonstrate a significant decline in measles cases following the introduction of vaccination programs. The data reveal a clear correlation between the initiation of vaccination campaigns and the subsequent reduction in measles incidence, irrespective of the year of introduction. Additionally, this analysis briefly explores data from Norway, which, while less granular, corroborates the observed pattern. Furthermore, we include an analysis of Egypt, where vaccination coverage gradually increased and resulted in the eventual elimination of recurring outbreaks.

Introduction

Measles, a highly contagious viral disease, was a major public health concern throughout the mid-20th century, leading to substantial morbidity and mortality worldwide. The development and implementation of measles vaccines marked a turning point in combating the disease. This paper investigates the temporal relationship between the introduction of measles vaccination campaigns and the reduction in measles incidence and mortality in the UK, US, USSR, Norway and Egypt.

Methods

Historical measles incidence data were collected from official health records and national statistical reports for the period 1940–1990 for the UK, US, USSR and Norway, and from the period 1975–2010 for Egypt. The analysis focuses on the timing of vaccination program implementation and subsequent changes in measles incidence. Countries were selected based on the availability of detailed annual data. For Norway, where only decadal data are available, trends were assessed qualitatively to compare with those of the primary countries. Data from Egypt were examined to explore the effects of delayed vaccination coverage expansion. For interpolating population data, a cubic spline method was employed to ensure smooth and accurate estimates between recorded data points.

A draft of this manuscript was reviewed and refined using ChatGPT (OpenAI) to enhance readability and language clarity. All scientific content and conclusions were developed by the author.

Results

1. **United States:** The measles vaccination program began in 1963. Within five years, measles incidence had declined dramatically, with cases dropping precipitously by 1968. This rapid reduction occurred despite no concurrent changes in other public health measures or socioeconomic conditions that could account for the decline.
2. **United Kingdom:** The UK introduced its measles vaccination program in 1968. Similarly to the US, measles cases declined shortly after the campaign began, with significant reductions observable within a few years.
3. **Soviet Union:** In the USSR, measles vaccination was also initiated in 1968. A comparable decline in incidence was noted, following the same pattern as in the UK and US, despite differing healthcare systems and demographic contexts.
4. **Norway:** Although annual data were not available, decadal statistics indicate a marked decrease in measles cases consistent with the period following vaccine introduction. While less precise, these data align with the trends observed in the other countries. According to Løvoll et al., the data for Norway should be interpreted with caution, as it may have been significantly underestimated [10].
5. **Egypt:** Measles vaccination in Egypt began in 1977, but vaccination coverage increased gradually, only surpassing 90% by 1999. Measles has a notably high reproduction number (R_0) of 12–18, making it essential to achieve vaccination coverage of 92–94% to effectively interrupt transmission, as highlighted by Guerra et al [11]. According to El Sayed et al, before reaching this threshold, measles outbreaks in Egypt occurred every 2–4 years [12]. Once the required coverage level was achieved, these recurring outbreaks ceased, illustrating the importance of sustained and widespread vaccination efforts in controlling measles.

Figure 1 illustrates the dynamics of measles incidence from 1940 to 1990 in the United States, the United Kingdom, the USSR, and Norway. Figure 2 illustrates the dynamics of measles incidence from 1975 to 2010 in Egypt.

Figures 3 and 4 highlight the phased reduction in measles mortality: the first phase occurred between the end of World War II and the beginning of vaccination campaigns (Figure 3), and the second phase followed the introduction of vaccination programs (Figure 4). The pre-vaccination decline in mortality can be attributed to several factors, including improvements in nutrition, sanitation, and access to healthcare, which reduced the severity of measles infections and associated complications. However, the steep decline observed during the vaccination era underscores the vaccine's pivotal role in preventing the disease. Statistics from the United Kingdom indicate that the primary cause of measles-related mortality is the adult death late effect of measles [5]. This highlights the critical role of vaccination in preventing mortality.

Measles outbreaks also exhibit periodicity, a distinct feature of its epidemiology. It is important to analyse not only overall trends but also the smoothing of peaks, particularly in the context of widespread vaccination. After vaccination coverage increased, peaks in both incidence and mortality were no longer observed.

Figure 1: Dynamics of measles incidence rate per 100000 people from 1940 to 1990 in the United States, the United Kingdom, the USSR, and Norway. Data: Our World in Data [1], PBS NewsHour [2], United States Census Bureau [3], Office for National Statistics [4], UK Health Security Agency[5], Løvoll Ø, Sandbu S [6], Ardabatskaya ES, Ardabatskiy SA, Eremeeva ZG [7]. Chart created by the author.

Figure 2: Dynamics of measles incidence rate per 100000 people from 1975 to 2010 in Egypt. Data: World Health Organization [8], Egypt State Information Service [9]. Chart created by the author.

Figure 3: Dynamics of measles mortality rate per 100000 people from 1940 to 1990 in the United States, the United Kingdom, and Norway. Data: Our World in Data [1], PBS NewsHour [2], United States Census Bureau [3], Office for National Statistics [4], UK Health Security Agency[5], Løvoll Ø, Sandbu S [6]. Chart created by the author.

Figure 4: Dynamics of measles mortality rate per 100000 people from 1960 to 1990 in the United States, the United Kingdom, and Norway. Data: Our World in Data [1], PBS NewsHour [2], United States Census Bureau [3], Office for National Statistics [4], UK Health Security Agency[5], Løvoll Ø, Sandbu S [6]. Chart created by the author.

Discussion

The findings strongly support the conclusion that vaccination campaigns were the primary driver of measles incidence reduction in reducing measles incidence and mortality across the studied countries. The consistency of the temporal patterns – despite variations in the year vaccination programs began – provides compelling evidence that the observed declines cannot be attributed to unrelated factors such as improved sanitation or general public health improvements. The case of Egypt highlights the challenges of achieving high vaccination coverage in regions with slower implementation rates and underscores the necessity of reaching critical coverage thresholds to prevent outbreaks.

Conclusion

This study underscores the decisive impact of vaccination on measles control, demonstrating a clear link between immunization efforts and disease reduction. The Egyptian case highlights the importance of sustained, high coverage to ensure long-term success. Future research should expand the geographical scope, assess the long-term effects of vaccination on eradication efforts, and explore factors such as the benefits of a second vaccine dose and potential delayed mortality due to measles complications. Additionally, given the observed demographic changes in birth rates, further analysis of population dynamics and age-specific measles patterns would be valuable.

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